

Research Article

DOI:doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.15255051

PRODUCTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CABBAGE WASTE BRIQUETTE FOR DOMESTIC HEATING USING CASSAVA STARCH AS BINDER

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the production and characterization of briquettes obtained from cabbage waste, using cassava starch as a binding agent via a locally fabricated briquetting machine, for domestic heating. The cabbage waste briquette was evaluated for properties such as calorific value (Q) 165 Kcal/g, moisture (MC) 12.0%, ash (AC) 35.4 % contents, and a volatile matters (VM) 10.8 %. A comparative water boiling test was conducted on the formed briquette and corn stalk fuel. The result show that 2 kg of the produced briquettes exhibit sufficient burning properties after boiling 5 liters of water in 45 minutes, while the same 2 kg of corn stalk boils the same volume of water in 60 minutes, demonstrating their potential as a fuel source. This research highlights the feasibility of using cabbage waste briquettes as an alternative energy source, contributing to reduced environmental impact and promoting sustainable waste management practices and energy generation in urban and rural areas.

Keywords: Cabbage; Corn Stalk; Cassava Starch; Briquette

INTRODUCTION

Biomass, particularly agricultural residues seem to be one of the most promising energy resources for developing countries [1]. Agricultural biomass residues are sources of renewable and sustainable biofuels which can contribute significantly to mitigating the effect of greenhouse gas emissions, if properly managed and utilized [2]. Due to inefficient use and improper methods of disposal of agricultural residue and paper, these materials tend to pollute the environment, thereby posing a health risk and hazard to man and the ecology. To curb the menace posed by these materials, efforts are to be geared towards controlling pollution resulting from these materials by converting them to briquettes [3]. Agricultural residues in their natural forms will not bring a desired result because, they are mostly loose, low-density materials in addition to the fact that their combustion cannot be effectively controlled [2]. The persistent energy challenges have resulted in making researchers across the globe seek alternative sources of energy that are not only environmentally friendly but cost-effective. One of such alternatives is the making of briquettes for heating [4].

Agricultural wastes are the most promising energy resource for developing countries like ours. The decreasing availability of fuel woods has necessitated efforts to be made towards efficient utilization of agricultural wastes. These wastes have acquired considerable importance as fuels for many purposes, for instance, domestic cooking and industrial heating. Some of these agricultural wastes, for example, coconut shells, wood pulp, and wood waste can be utilized directly as fuels [5]. Energy and fuels are the important links in civilization and human development. The issues associated with the use of fossil fuels, demand and supply gap, ever-increasing prices, global warming, and other environmental issues made the world think of alternate sources of energy like solar, wind, ocean, and biomass which are the only Indigenous renewable energy sources capable of replacing a large amount of solid, liquid and gaseous fossil fuel [6]. Biomass energy has been attracted as one of the potential alternatives as it is an ideal renewable energy source with several advantages like lower sulfur, CO₂ neutral emission, and abundant availability generally in the form of waste from agriculture as well as other sources [7]

Bioenergy derived from biomass is a promising, inexhaustible, sustainable source and can help in minimizing the rising environmental, economic, and technological issues related to depleting fossil fuels. The utilization of waste for deriving secondary fuel has received worldwide acceptance as it can provide fuel and at the same time solution to waste disposal maintaining the environment. The population across the globe is increasingly getting inclined towards healthy and processed food products, about one-third of it gets wasted globally and accounts roughly 40-50% of root crops, fruits, and vegetables at various stages like agricultural production, post-harvest handling and storage, processing and packaging, distribution and consumption [7]. For food losses in developing countries, more than 40% loss occur at post-harvest and processing levels, while in industrialized countries, almost the same losses occur at retail and consumer levels [7]. The present study focuses on the strategic application of thermochemical conversion of vegetable wastes into environmentally friendly and low-cost production of biofuel. A briquette is a block of compressed coal, biomass, or charcoal dust used as fuel to start and maintain fire. The term briquette is a French word "Brique", meaning brick [8]. Briquetting is the process of compacting low-density and loose combustible organic materials that are inefficient into high-density solid fuel of convenient shapes. Briquetting improves the physical, chemical and combustion properties of the raw materials [9]. It can be regarded as a waste control measure in the case of production of briquettes from agricultural wastes. However, depending on the material of interest, briquetting can be used to provide a fuel source as a preventive measure to many ecological problems. Briquetting is a high-pressure process that can be done at elevated temperature or ambient temperature [10] depending on the technology one wants to employ. During this process, fine material is compacted into a regular shape and size which does not separate during transportation, storage or combustion. In some briquetting techniques, the materials are simply compressed without addition of binder (binder less briquettes), while in some, adhesive material is added to assist in holding the particles of the material together [11]. The shape and size of briquettes are dependent on the mold, while the appearance and (calorific values) are dependent on the type of feedstock and the level of compactness [12].

Good quality briquettes were produced from dried loose vegetable market wastes without using any external binder. These briquettes can be used as a fuel in domestic cook stoves, boilers, and gasifiers, the general waste to energy conversion process, and energy use of vegetable market waste [13]. Economically, the production of briquettes using agricultural waste and locally available binders can create new opportunities for rural communities, contributing to energy security and sustainable development [14].

Biomass briquettes are a form of renewable energy that are made from various types of agricultural and forestry waste. Their composition can vary depending on the type of biomass available and the specific production process used. The biomass briquettes is composed of Primary Raw Materials (Agricultural Waste): which includes materials such as rice husks, peanut shells, coconut husks, coffee husks, and straw etc. These wastes are typically by-products of agricultural processes and are often available in large quantities; binding agents. which include organic binders such as starch, molasses, or inorganic binders are used to hold the briquette together. The use of binders can depend on the specific type of biomass and the desired properties of the final briquette. The availability of energy in the rural as well as urban areas globally is fast becoming a great challenge with the high cost of cooking gas and kerosene and environmental problems associated with firewood [13]. Electricity is erratic and unreliable. Other sources of energy that include sunlight, geothermal power, wind and tidal movements, are becoming not economically now for large-scale uses, and cannot be affordable especially for the rural and semi urban dwellers [15]. This has drawn attention to the need for an urgent transition to a more sustainable energy system that would be affordable and eco-friendly [16]. As such this research is on the prospects of using Agro-wastes and other biomass for the production of solid fuels called briquettes which would serve as substitutes and alternative to the depleting non-renewable energy sources.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material Collection

The cabbage waste was collected in Jos, Plateau State and transported to Maiduguri in a clean polyethene bags, then was shade-dried for 7 days in the Research Laboratory of the Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry, University of Maiduguri for further analysis, while the cassava starch was bought at Moromoro Market in Maiduguri, Borno State

Equipment

The equipment's used for this study were: mixing bowl, stirrer, heating gas, Sievers, aluminum cooking pot, beaker (500mL), mortar and pestle, locally fabricated briquetting machine with fabricated cylindrical molds, locally fabricated stove, Stopwatch, thermometer, weigh balance, porcelain crucible, oven, desiccator.

Methods

Preparation of the biomass Sample

The dry cabbage wastes were pulverized into fine particles using a mortar and pestle, sieved with a 1mm sieve and stored for use. A cassava starch paste was prepared, using hot water at a temperature of 100 °C the prepared paste is kept for further usage.

Briquetting Process

Using the Method adopted by [17] with little modification the pulverized cabbage waste was screened from stones and other impurities that might inhibit proper briquettes formation. hot water was boiled and mixed with the starch already mixed with cold water to produce a paste or sticky gel. The prepared sample is further blended with the cassava starch paste at the ratio of 4:1 to obtain a semi-solid mixture. Using the discontinuous process, the blended mixture was packed and loaded into the cylindrical mold and later compressed by weight for some time using the locally fabricated machine, the compressed briquette is extruded and dry in the laboratory for two weeks to achieve a proper drying before analysis.

Plate 1: Produced Cabbage Waste briquettes

Characterization of Briquette Sample

Proximate Analysis

Proximate Analysis is a standardized procedure that gives an idea of the bulk component that makes up a fuel, and was done to determine the average percentage Ash and moisture contents, volatile matter, percentage carbon contents of the briquette formed, the procedure of [18] was adopted.

Determination of Moisture Content

The initial moisture content of the briquette was determined according to the method used by [19] with slight modification, 10g sample was weighed and dried at a temperature of 150°C in a hot air oven until the constant weight of the sample was recorded using analytical weighing balance. The weight was recorded after and before putting into oven. The initial moisture content was calculated using the equation below.

$$MC (\% \text{ wb}) = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where W_1 is the initial weight, W_2 is the final weight or dry weight of the sample

Determination of Ash content

Six grams (6g) portion of sample was placed in a pre-weight porcelain crucible and transferred into a preheated oven at a temperature of 600°C for 5hrs., and the crucible and its content was transferred into the desiccator and allowed to cool. The crucible and its content were reweighed and a new weight was taken, the method used by [17] was adopted and the percentage Ash content can be calculated using the formula below.

$$AC (\%) = \frac{W_2}{W_1} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where W_2 is the weight of Ash at cooling, W_1 is the original weight of dry sample and AC is Ash Content.

Determination of Volatile Matters

A portion (10 g) of the sample was heated to about 300 °C for 30 min in a partially closed crucible in an oven. The crucible and its content were retrieved and cooled in a desiccator. The difference in weight was recorded, and the volatile matter was calculated using the equation:

$$VM = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where, VM = Volatile Matter. W_1 = Original Weight of sample. W_2 = Weight of the sample after cooling [17].

Determination of Fixed Carbon Content

The method used by [17] was adopted. The percentage fixed carbon (PFC) was computed by subtracting the sum of PVM (percentage volatile matters) and PAC (percentage ash content) from 100 as shown in the Equation 4:

$$\text{Fixed Carbon} = 100\% - (PAC + PVM) \dots\dots\dots 4$$

Determination of Water Boiling Test

The water boiling test is a measure of the time it takes to give a quantity of fuel to heat and boil a given quantity of water. the method described by [6,18], with little modification, was adopted. A known mass of briquette and corn stalk were measured, first the briquette sample was stacked in a local fabricated stove, while the corn stalk was stacked in a different stove. Both stoves were ignited and as soon as the flame stabilized for 2 minutes, two aluminum pots containing 5 liters of water each were mounted on the stoves, a stopwatch was activated. The initial temperature of the water was noted and thereafter readings were obtained every 5 mins. interval using a thermometer. Both the contents of the stoves were terminated after attaining boiling points.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the physical properties of the formed briquette and revealed that it has a large volume of 133.5cm^3 and a mass of 140.0g which is an indication that it will be able to maintain combustion for long period. The density of the briquette was found to be 1.05g/cm^3 which is same as density obtained for sawdust charcoal briquette reported by [19]. This result aligns with the range recommend by [6] for biomass briquette produced by manual screw extrusion process. These parameter shows that the briquette will not crumble during transportation and storage because the value obtain for the density is moderate, and the cassava starch binder used does not absorb moisture that contribute to the briquette durability and stored over a long period of time. Also, the physical condition of the briquette revealed that the external surface is rough, having a brown color, these are obtained by physical observation, and is a parameter to maintain long-term efficient burning.

Table 1: Physical properties of Produced Briquette

Colour	Texture	M (g)	L (mm)	D (mm)	V (cm^3)	Density(g/cm^3)
Brown	Rough	140.0	150.0	50	133.5	1.05

Table 2 shows the proximate analysis of the formed briquette sample indicating that the calorific value (Q) is 165 Kcal/g while moisture and ash (MC and AC) contents ranges from 12.0 to 35.4 % for cabbage waste/ cassava starch formulation, according to [9] 18% moisture content and below shows a material does not contain free water but the water that is chemically bonded with the material this means that the material is dry and its physicochemical properties would not be influence by moisture content thereby enhances the burning property. However, it is important to analyze various properties of briquette at similar range of moisture content, therefore considering the moisture content of the briquette formed, it is recommended for generating heat, the ash content of the briquette produced using the formulation of cabbage waste and cassava starch paste, results to 35.4%. This result is in the same range as that seen with sawdust and cassava starch paste formulation with 33.8% Ash content as revealed by [17]. It is advantageous when Briquette has a lower percentage of Ash content, which makes them burn at a high rate with high heating value. However, the tolerance level of ash content is below 4% as described by [15]. In this regard, the Ash content of this briquette is within an accepted range for solid fuel. The result also shows that the produced briquette has high volatile matter (VM) of 10.8 which accounts for its high energy required to burn off the volatile matter content before the release of its heat energy. The result fall within the limits reported by [20].

Table 2: Proximate Analysis of Produced Briquette

Q (Kcal/g)	MC (%)	AC (%)	VM (%)
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Cabbage waste	165	12.0	35.4	10.8
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Table 3 shows the water boiling test of briquette (cabbage waste briquette) versus cornstalks, the water boiling rate is the measure of the fuel burning efficiency value. Based on the result obtain for water boiling test of the briquette sample, it shows that variation of temperature with time for cabbage waste briquette and cornstalks, at time 0 the briquette sample raised the temperature of 5litres of water to 25 °C while cornstalk attained at 29 °C, after 5 minutes interval the briquette sample raised the same volume of water to the temperature of 51 °C and cornstalks 45°C, subsequently at 10, 15, 20, 25, to 30 minutes interval the briquette sample raised the temperature of the water from 60, 68, 70, 82, and 90 °C and cornstalk raised the same volume of water at those times from 48, 55, 58, 65 to 68 °C, at 45minute the briquette sample raised the temperature of 5 litres of water to 100 °C while the cornstalk raised the temperature of the same 5 litres of water to 100°C at 60 minute. The briquette shows better combustion characteristics compared to the cornstalk, which burns slowly from 29 °C in 0 minute through 100 °C in 60 minutes. This difference can be observed in the graph of temperature versus time for both the cabbage waste briquette and the cornstalk and shown on the graph below. This finding reveals that the briquette burns with great heat in a shorter period of time than the cornstalk.

Table 3: Determination of Water boiling Test on the Produced Briquette

S/No	Time(s)	Briquette Temp. (°C)	Corn Stalk Temp. (°C)
1	0	25	29
2	5	51	45
3	10	60	48
4	15	68	55
5	20	70	58
6	25	82	65
7	30	90	68
8	35	95	72
9	40	98	80
10	45	100	85
11	50	-	90
12	55	-	95
13	60	-	100

Figure 1: Graph of Water Boiling Test of Briquette Sample versus Cornstalk

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the production and characterization of cabbage waste briquettes using cassava starch as a binder show promising potential energy for domestic heating applications. Utilizing cabbage waste not only provides an effective method of waste management but also contributes to renewable energy resources by reducing

overdependence on traditional firewood, charcoal and fossil fuels. The addition of cassava starch as a binder result in a briquette with suitable compressive strength, calorific value, combustion properties, and does not absorb moisture during storage, making the briquette a viable, eco-friendly alternative for heating. This approach not only mitigates environmental issues associated with agricultural waste disposal, but also supports sustainable energy practices, aligning with the goals of reducing carbon emissions and promoting green energy solutions in this global trend of green chemistry.

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